

An Appraisal of the Primacy of Religion in Responding to Nigerian Security Challenges

Vitalis Terhemba Anaana Ph.D

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi
anaanavt@yahoo.com

Boniface Msugh Ahura Ph.D

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi-Nigeria
ahuraboniface@gmail.com

Lembi Jamima

Department of Religious Studies, Gombe State University, Gombe-Nigeria

Abstract

Religious crises that defined the twentieth century have continued in the twenty first century where innocent people continue to suffer and die every day especially in Northern Nigeria. Despite the urgent need for solidarity for peace, unity, tolerance and co-operation, certain circles are perceived to be inciting religious conflicts/crises, particularly between the two major religious groups (Islam and Christianity) in Nigeria. Religious crises in Nigeria are the major root causes of security challenges. This research which is historical, comparative and descriptive in nature examined the primacy of religion in Nigeria's security challenges in the twentieth and twenty first century. The study found out that, religion has been ascertained as the primary force for social, political and economic progress of the Nigerian nation over the years but today it is the opposite. In the same disposition, religion is also known to be the primacy of security challenges in Nigeria today contrary to what was obtainable in the 20th century. Findings also revealed that, the effects of this primacy of religion in Nigerian security challenges today are found in economic, social, political, educational, health and religious aspects. The study therefore concluded with adequate recommendations for a positive way forward that, the government of Nigeria as a matter of urgency needs to comparatively checkmate the practice and operations of religions in Nigeria today and ensure the effective operation of the rule of law at all levels of government. The study also recommends that one of the best ways of preventing such disasters in Nigerian society is to strengthen the implementation of dialogue and co-operation between these religions in order to prevent the future manifestations of these religious crises in Nigeria for peaceful co-existence and national integration.

Keywords: Religions, Religious Conflict, Crisis, Security Challenges, Peace, Development.

Introduction

Over the years, history has it that, religion has proven to be the primary force for social progress motivating individual to develop spiritual qualities and empowering moral suasion and to contribute to the betterment of communities. Religion is also responsible for the universal spiritual principle which lies at the heart of religious tolerance, compassion, love, justice, kindness, humility, sacrifice, trustworthiness, dedication to the wellbeing and unity of the nation. In the same vein, it must be acknowledged that, the perversion of religion has been a primary cause of social disintegration, intolerance, hatred, sexism, poverty, oppression and warfare down through the ages. Indeed, many of those highlighted by the social summit process can be traced to the corruption and misuse of religious doctrines, teachings and authority. It is obvious that, if religion is to help meet the manifold challenges confronting the world community, it must be free of ignorance, prejudice and animosity.

Religious conflicts and violence are here seen as differing level of antagonism and armed battles that occur between and amongst religious bodies and groups. Included in these contradictions is the economic dimension. The position of this study is that the primacy of religion in Nigeria's security challenges is the representation of

religious conflicts and violence at all facets of human social living. This duly implies that, solving them would require a more wholistic attention including in particular resolving the contradictions that produce them at the economy, the political or the state, and of course, the ideological instance. In Nigeria, most of the security challenges we experienced are as a direct result of religious crises. Kukah affirmed this that, religion plays a major role in many nations' security challenges. There is massive destruction of lives and properties due to human insecurity, even investors are declining to come and invest in Nigerian's economy. Industries have been shut down in many places, power sector in the affected areas have been shut down and the dividends of democracy are lacking¹. The study seeks to therefore examine the past and the present security challenges in Nigeria in order to ascertain how religion is the root cause of the devastating security challenges experienced in contemporary Nigerian society. The study went further to identify the effects of these security challenges in Nigeria and what measures can be done to curb the problem of security challenges caused by religions in Nigeria today.

Conceptual Clarification

Religion: Religion is a worldwide phenomenon that has played a part in all human culture and tradition. It is a distinctive set of beliefs, rituals, doctrines, institutions and practices that enables members of that tradition to establish, maintain and celebrate a meaningful world"². Religion may also be defined as a sacred engagement which is believed to be a spiritual reality. Religion can better be understood as a regulated pattern of life of a people in which experiences, beliefs and knowledge are reflected in man's conception of himself in relation to others, his social world, the physical as well as the metaphysical world.

The elements of beliefs and practices with the former finding expression in the latter are common even with concepts outside religion.³ However, from which angle or no matter how one defines religion, two elements stand out clearly: beliefs and practices. Affirming the above, Radcliff Brown opines that "any religion normally involves certain ideas or beliefs on the one hand, and on the other hand, a certain observance."⁴ That is religion can also be defined as a particular system of faith and worship, and/or a controlling influence on one's life.

Religious Crises/Conflicts: According to Kadayifci, religious conflicts are conflicts that often take place among religious communities that live in close proximity and whose histories are filled with hostility, resentment, trauma and violence.⁵ Conflict is a struggle over values and claims to scarce resource status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure or eliminate the rivals. It entails a physical confrontation between parties.⁶ By religious conflict, it means a situation in which the relationship between members of one religious group and another are characterised by lack of cordiality, peaceful co-existence, mutual suspicion and fear, and a tendency towards violent confrontation.

Security: Understanding the meaning of security has been generating a great debate among scholars in recent time, the experience of the world in recent time emphasizes a paradigm shift in security discourse. Traditionally, the state is the custodian and ultimate beneficiary of the monopoly use of violence as advocated by Max Weber. Any internal or external threat to challenging the authority of the state in monopolising violence was considered as a security challenges.⁷ From the fore going, it is very clear that religion is a double-edged sword institution. Religion can produce insecurity and at the same time religion can be used as a tool to enhance security in a country like Nigeria.

Religious Crises in Nigeria

Religious crisis is a disagreement or disunity between two groups or one religion and or different religious group that militate against coherent existence or practice within or without themselves. This situation has existed from time immemorial in Nigeria. In such occasions, it has resulted to factions and denominations. In another development it could be Christianity versus Muslims, which we experience much often in Nigeria. Today, this freedom seems threatened by some religious zealots, mostly Muslims. They want to force others to accept their own mode of worship as the only acceptable one.⁸

Consequently, it is widely accepted that, of all religions in Nigeria, Islam maintained the record of being the most bloody and controversial by ways of demonstration of faiths. This assertion may be regarded as a historical legacy rather than an aberration. Right from time immemorial Islamic activities have been associated with violence as a means of purification or as a unification of its followers. Unfortunately, this religion violence grows in intensity owing to the surprising doctrine that one who stubbornly dies in the course of fighting the *infidels* will inevitably find himself in (Al-Jannah) Heaven or paradise.⁹

One of the most recent agents of religious crisis in Nigeria today is "*Boko Haram* and Fulani Herdsmen where Islamic fundamentalists is campaigning against anything Western claiming that its adherents were not allowed by the Bauchi State Government to publicly practice their religion as well as win more souls to the sect. Another agent that brought a new pattern now is the Fulani Herdsmen, attacking every community that is not theirs to settle hence the right of movement applied to all people. In order to have a clear understanding of the whole issue, there is need to dig down into the origin and concept of the doctrine of "*Boko Haram*."¹⁰

The word *Boko Haram* may be seen as new from a shallow perspective, but the concept started off from Northern Nigeria, when Europeans under the pretext of colonialism began to play double cards, by introducing their type of education alongside Christianity in the Muslim dominated North that was already operating on sound Islamic Jurisdiction, distinctive societal values and administration, as well as comprehensive Islamic educational system due to long time romance with the Arab World and the effects of the 19th century Islamic *Jihad* led by Sheikh Usman Dan Fodio.¹¹

As a result of what the Northerners perceived as a ploy by Europeans to rubbish their religious values and replace it with Christianity in the first instance, and the ample evidence of practical steps to mask-and-serve Christianity in the Western education by Christian missionaries, the Northern Muslims began to declare that the education the Europeans claimed to be dispensing called *Boko* is *haram*, which means "*Boko*" (European education) "*Haram*" (forbidden). Therefore, *Boko Haram* means European education is forbidden.¹² Owing to this clash of dissimilar ideologies between Christian imperialists and the Northern Muslim Communities, many parents had to withdraw their children in order to save their belief and moral values from being contaminated.

In some instances, it was agreed that this event is one of the major reasons behind the North's poor participation in "Western Education" today. After more than a century, those olden days local Muslim folks that resisted "*Boko*" in the North and without foot dragging declared it "*Haram*", are today being vindicated by the attitude of our *Boko* trained workforce. Over the years, Nigerian graduates of *Boko* (Western Education) in almost all walks of life have proved beyond any doubt that they are self-centered and irresponsible in their conducts. They are the looters of public treasury, tacticians of bribery and corruption, promoters of injustice, election riggers, liars and assassins.¹³

According to Yusuf, *Boko Haram* is a simple protest over the perceived and apparent moral decay associated with western educational system and the need to indoctrinate the fear of Allah alone and de-emphasise the pursuance of evil principles and practices that tow the system and our lifestyle in the negative direction. Pitifully, this is the simple justice that many people couldn't do to Yusuf's profound argument on Western education system simply because the man does not agree to decorating fraudulent empire. For example, Allah has forbidden any gathering where men and women mingle together freely in the same environment except under transient abnormal circumstance that one doesn't have any control over. But in our universities, men and women mingle together, and it is against the will of Allah.¹⁴

Sheikh Muhammed Yusuf looked around for remedy against the evils associated with our educational system, against the evil of election rigger, against the evils of corrupt judges, against the evils of our security organisations, against the evils of treasury looters, against perversion by some Muslims and traditional rulers (who benefits from the 19th century *Jihad*), but found it nowhere within the sphere of the Westerly influenced system. Yusuf began to device and implement what he believes is the best solution to counter the mess of our own brand of Westernisation.¹⁵

First, he started by enjoining people to do only those things approved by Allah no matter how such may appear in the eyes of the custodians of corruption, and keep away from anything disapproved by Allah, no matter the material benefits attached. He urged Muslims to stick to the Qur'an and the Hadith of the prophet, read it constantly, memorising it, understanding it and putting it in practice. Certainly, Prophet Muhammad has enjoined Muslims on importance of military training and the need to keep arms at all times.¹⁶

It was learnt that, member of the sect had been planning a demonstration in Bauchi for a long time but were not given the chance because of the fear by government that their doctrine, if allowed to be practice publicly, would cause religious crisis, considering the fact that the teachings were completely contrary to those of other Islamic sects as regards peaceful coexistence. The sect members in their hundreds trooped to Dutsen Tansni Police Station in the early hours of the date and attacked it. They destroyed everything they could lay their hands on but could not break into the armoury. The police fought the Fundamentalists to a standstill and overpowered them and arrested over a hundred of them.¹⁷

President Yar' Adua in dealing with *Boko Haram* proponents ruthlessly, he instructed his security forces to take whatever measure they feel is necessary to do away with them. Many of them were overwhelm by the Nigerian Securities forces apparent demonstration of cruelty, and the elaborate media coverage the event enjoyed, as if it was intended to showcase the practicality of some particular Nazi theories on Nigerian citizens. On that fateful day 26th July, 2009, the trouble escalated in the afternoon, before the close of the day, over 100 people suspected to be sharing the ideology of *Boko Haram* were killed by Police and the Army, with some outrageous figure of mass arrests.¹⁸

The same incidence occurred in Maiduguri, in Potiskum and other Northern towns and cities. When Yusuf and his lieutenants were over powered the subsequent days, the death toll was already on four digits. Muhammad Yusuf was declared wanted or alive. Eventually he was caught alive by the Army and handed over to Police authorities alive shortly after, the Police remembered Yar Adua's directive and saw it was necessary to kill him right away without being tried. They gave him multiple shots at close range, and declared him dead, thereby bridging his fundamental human right.¹⁹

The Primacy of Religion in Nigerian Security Challenges

In recent times, religion has become a major issue, leading to mutual condemnation. There is deep suspicion, fears and anxiety in the relationship between Muslims and Christians, which is oftentimes leading to violence and killings, especially in Northern Region. As a result of the various religious conflicts, people have been killed, injured And or displaced. Properties are destroyed, businesses closed down and investors are scared away and communities are split along religious lines. Worse still, the effect of religious rivalry is reflected in the media, which is regarded as the fourth estate of the realm, the agenda setter, force multiplier and gate keeper.²⁰

On the political front, since independence in 1960, our political parties have always reflected ethnic patterns and this has posed a challenge of managing multiparty democracy in a multi religious nation like ours. The politics of religion has denied us the opportunity for census which we require for national planning purposes, as we always attach population to the share of the so-called national cake and other advantages. Nigerians have been arguing as to whether Muslims are more in number or it is 50/50 and forgetting that there are citizens who are neither Muslims nor Christians.²¹

Obviously both men and women in attempt to practice religion have given up not their possession but also their lives. Human being from time immersed, born into wealth and destined to inherit great possession from their relation have renounced them and turned themselves into beggars for their religious beliefs.²² Thus, religion has such a powerful grip on man that it cannot be ignored in human society. In another development, the concept of God is very cardinal to the issue of religion. Furthermore, the existence of God is an incomprehensible mystery that different religious conceive of him. It is not possible for any religion to hold entire knowledge of God, but each of them has their own fragmental and limitation to the aspects they understood God (<http://articlesng.com/religious-crisis-nigeria>).

Religion has remained a core and a largely divisive part of the politics of religions and ethnicity in Nigeria. Raw appeal to the religious persuasion of candidates for public office is common. The Bible and the Qur'an have become part of the staple of playing the divide and conquer strategy in the geo-politics of the country of almost 200m largely energetic citizens. It has been so even long before Nigeria's political independence of October 1st, 1960. In fact, since the British colonialist, Lord Lugard, led the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Protectorates regions of Nigeria in 1914. The Sokoto Caliphate, the Roman Catholic Church and the Anglican Church and its variations have had ample engagement on who governs Nigeria. This reality was underscored by power of the Sultan of Sokoto since 1890s until the late and infamous Gen. Sani. Abacha came and plucked the previously influential Ibrahim Dasuki from the throne.²³

Nigeria's "human rights" record remains poor and government officials at all levels continue to commit serious abuses. The U.S. Department of State declares that, the most significant human rights problems in Nigeria are extrajudicial killings and use of excessive force by security forces, arbitrary arrests, impunity for abuses by security forces, prolonged pretrial detention, judicial corruption and executive influence on the judiciary, rape, torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment of prisoners, detainees and suspects, harsh and life-threatening prison and detention center conditions, human trafficking for the purpose of prostitution and forced labour, societal violence and vigilante killings, child labour, child abuse and child sexual exploitation, female genital mutilation, domestic violence discrimination based on sex, ethnicity and religion.

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria established the fundamental Human Right for the country. According to the 1999 Constitution, every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance. No person attending any place of education shall be required to receive religious instruction or to take part in or attend any religious ceremony or observance if such instruction ceremony relates to a religion other than his own. No religious community or denomination shall be prevented from providing religious instruction for pupils of that community or denomination in any place of education maintained wholly by that community or denomination. Nothing in this section shall entitle any person from take part in the activity or be member of a secret society. However, the Twelve Northern States in Nigeria that have adopted the Sharia Penal code includes; Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Jigawa, Niger, Sokoto, Yobe and Zamfara. The *Sharia* penal code only applies to Muslims. It provides harsh sentence for alcohol consumption, infidelity and theft. Christian Pastors in Nigeria have been accused of involvement in the torturing and killing of children accused of witchcraft. Over the past decade, over 1000 children have been murdered as witches.²⁴

Religious Factors as a Major Source of Insecurity in Nigeria

As indicated earlier on, every geopolitical zone of the country had tasted the bitter pill of ethno-religious violence. While both ethnic and religious crises have nearly torn the Northern part of the country into pieces, the South-Western part faces theirs in different dimensions. In the Niger-Delta zone, the militants' youth have the place hot for expatriates working in the oil industries making the place virtually ungovernable for the government. The *Bakassi* boys and the MASSOB took over the South-East with the aim of liberating their zone from Nigeria and stay alone to control the natural resources on their land. From this one, one observes that different factors are responsible of ethno-religious crises in Nigeria.²⁵

It cannot be doubted that Nigeria is naturally endowed with natural resources and naturally blessed with fertile land that is good for both cash crops and food crops and it has high potential for industrial and economic development. The discovery of crude oil is an additional advantage to the country and this serves as her major foreign exchange income. In spite of these divine blessings, it is sad to note that the country is scored low in terms of human development. The 1998 human development report of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) states that in Nigeria, life expectancy is 52years compared to 75years in developed countries while one-third of the people live not up to 40years.

Infant mortality is 79 out of 1000 births, compared to 10 in developed countries, mortality rate of children under 5 years are stunted due to malnutrition, only 44 percent of adult population are literate, 49 and 70 percent, respectively have no access to safe portable water in the urban and rural areas, 49 percent have no access to basic health facilities and 48.5 percent live in poverty compared to 43 percent in 2015.²⁶ In his statistical analysis, Adebayo claimed that in 1996, the number of people bitten by excessive poverty in Nigeria was 39.2 million representing 65.6 percent of the population as against 17.7 million representing 28.1 percent of the Nigerian population in 1980 and the current statistics today is the worst.²⁷

Another reason responsible for religious crises in Nigeria is wrong interpretation of the scriptures by those who claim authority to the interpretation of the holy books. If not so, one wonders why people act contrary to the teaching of the scriptures in matters pertaining to peaceful co-existence, unity and sanctuary of life, and property. As it is a serious diseases and ignorance to claim authority to knowledge, many of our so called 'religious leaders' use their shallow knowledge to interpret the scriptures to suit their selfish end banking on the ignorance of their followers. Lamenting on practice of religions among its adherent, Adebayo identified some factors responsible for using religion as an instrument of polarisation among which is leadership tussle; has also culminated in the proliferation of many denominations in the country. Also, sectarian jingoism, as well as excessive patriotism to one's religious sect, which consequently transformed to fanaticism, is another major factor contributing to social menace²⁸. In conclusion, many other factors have been identified as the causes of religious violence in Nigeria. These include selfishness, agreed, injustice, poverty, do or die politics, love of money, accumulation of wealth, revolt, repression, immorality and ignorance.

Religion as a Panacea to the Challenges of Peace and Security in Nigeria

The actualization of the dream of religion to form an integrating force for Nigeria can be fulfilled when it is able to govern the kind of function it performs. Religion should not be influence by bribes, invitation to be members of committees or commission. Religious leaders must as a point of duty provide the relation between religion and politics that cannot be denied or forgotten because there is no aspect of human life from which God can be excluded. The fact is that politics dealing with the affairs of human life call for the presence of God. Religious leaders must give a grassroots theologising which is a, project of employment potentially a revolutionary and explosive enterprise that is capable of unleashing a power among those who have hither to been powerless people will begin to think critically for themselves. Change is likely to be evolutionary because the reflection is done in the light of God; word which a fearful double-edged sword that judge the desires and thoughts of people hearts.²⁹

For the Christians, Jesus Christ had prayed "May all be one" (Jn. I 7:21). Scriptural scholars have termed this prayer "unity prayer" there is no doubt that Christ God-man was not aware of ravaging differences among people of same community especially regarding religious faith. It is a painful fact of life that there is no country that can boast of a single tribe, custom and religion even if there is a country in the world with a single tribe, it will have different cultures, where there is a nation with one tribe and one culture see that same nation cannot have all the people worship the same kinds of god and if there is even one god, the mode of worship will definitely be different because there are different people with different value system, codes of conduct and religious affiliations.

In spite of this reality, there is even, great need for unity amidst these wide differences. The goal of nation's integration is paramount to the mind of conscious and reasonable citizens in Nigeria today. As the saying goes: what you plant is what you are going to reap; as you lay your bed, as you sleep on it. What we are experiencing today is the result of what was obtained yesterday and the seeds of what we shall experience tomorrow are being sown today, whether these seeds are to be seen in terms of the political, social, economics, psychological or religious dimension, will be made easy from the way we handle the issues of religion and politics.³⁰

Many people think religion and politics are the two keys institutions that are responsible for the division and unity of the Nigerian nation. Political leaders must understand that they are called to serve and not to be

served. They must also know that Nigerians are better informed on issues concerning tribe and religion. Today, ethnicity and religiosity do not count in politics; the most important thing is who can deliver the expected goods. The kind of leadership that we need today in Nigeria is one that is objective, open, fair and just. Any leader that will encourage the disintegration of the nation by word or deeds must be rejected using all available means. We strongly agree with Daniel N. Klambutda, in his opinion that a leader who shows favoritism should be rejected as well as one who is indifferent to the plight of the poor and the less-privileged should not be given any support.³¹

A proper education of the different adherents will bring about the needed dialogue which will be built on the basis of equality, fair play, social justice and above all on objective reasoning. The task must exceed the quest for religious tolerances and acceptability of persons with inalienable human rights. Religion must contribute immensely to the education of the populace. It must encourage the position of political leaders who are dedicated, committed and selfless people with the fear of God. If this is true then we may be fighting an unproductive war by trying to bring mankind under one faith. It is clear from the forgone that religion though necessary in the political scene has been employed negatively in Nigeria.

Religious leaders are called upon to use their respected positions to influence events in politics positively by encouraging political leaders who are on the track and those who are not on the path that leads to peace and national development should be cautioned and if possible given open confrontations in order to nip the bud of crisis. It will be wrong for religious leaders to take side with the members of the executive, the legislature and the judiciary because they belong to his religion. The religious leaders especially the clergy must be critical and vociferous where corruption, discriminating and injustices are holding sway, but must not stop at criticizing the politicians when things are going wrong.³²

Other ways of actualizing the unity of purpose in Nigeria using religion as a formidable tool include that; Nigerian leaders should ensure that, the national policy on religion as enshrined in the constitution must be sustained. Talking about sustaining the policy is a way of saying that the government functionaries must differentiate their religious commitment from their religious obligations. The leaders must learn to be neutral in performing their functions. These are some of the ways religion can create an enabling society especially in Nigeria. Indeed, religion and politics must work hand-in-hand in this country on the basis of neutrality if we must move forward.

Recommendations

In the light of the above facts emerging from the study, the following recommended are hereby made: The government of Nigeria as a matter of urgency needs to ensure the effectiveness of the rule of law in all the levels of government in order to prevent the future manifestations of religious crisis in Nigeria. Positive preaching by religious leaders is essential. All religious leaders must deliberately cultivate cordial and harmonious relationship and interactions with other religious faith rather than projecting evil and greedy tendencies. They should also educate their members on the need to the values of tolerance, dialogue, healthy debate for peaceful co-existence. The leaders of Christians and Muslims must stand for the truth of God Almighty they claimed preached in order to encourage and to preach to their adherents on the urgent need for peaceful co-existence with one another hence the serve one and the same God. Government should develop programs or projects that can bring both Christians and Muslims together especially on the basis of inter-marriage and inter-religious dialogue. Non-Governmental organisations (NGOS) who are concerned with the peace and unity of Nigeria should also help to sensitise and create awareness to all Nigerians on the urgent need to live in peace and unity to attract more development and progress of our nation. Finally, government of Nigeria should as a matter of urgency implement the teaching of moral education particularly comparative religious dialogue at the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in order to prevent the future occurrence of religious crisis in Northern Nigeria.

Conclusion

The primacy of religion in Nigeria's security challenges has been critically analysed on the fact that there is no known society where religion does not exist and that more recently, religion in Nigeria has become a major issue leading to mutual condemnation, where there exist deep suspicion, fears and anxiety in the relationship between Muslims and Christians, These at most times leads to violence especially in the North region and the result of this various religious crises are massive destruction of human lives and properties, displacement of people and many other consequences.

The study reveals that, religion plays a major role in most Nigeria security challenges. Most of the security challenges are directly as a result of religious crises. This study has ascertained the extent to which the primacies of religion in Nigeria's security challenges are to economic insecurity, insecurity of human lives, social insecurity and political insecurity and many other aspects. Equally, this study is timely as it relates to a period that Nigeria is experiencing security a lot of challenges that are mostly religious crises. This study is therefore, a clarion call for all and sundry, the government, faith-based organisations, other agencies and the entire Nigerian people that love peace and unity to ensure that the present security challenges in Nigeria are tackled.

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